

CONSEQUENCES OF ENERGY MANAGEMENT MEASURES IN PRODUCTION PROCESS ON RES-BASED COGENERATION UNIT

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Abstract

Production plants combined with cogeneration units act as complex as living organisms. Slight changes in their operation parameters can lead to significant alterations of overall economic profit. This paper is focused on operation adjustments required for implementation of cost saving measures in large industrial plant producing pulp and paper equipped with cogeneration units and demonstrates benefits of low investment steam handling improvements in production process on RES-based electricity production. One of the largest steam consuming units in pulp and paper plant is paper machine. Paper machines serve for chemical and mechanical treatment of pulp fibres and their conversion into final paper product. The most heat demanding process is the paper drying. To achieve optimum drying profile for different final paper products, different steam pressure levels are required. Thermocompressor is often applied to produce a required-pressure steam from a low- and a high-pressure one. Thermocompressor under review served for raising the pressure of the low-pressure steam by 100 kPa. Thorough analysis including mass and energy balances of paper drying process and critical study of historical operating data records revealed that the thermocompressor could be shut down for ca. 13 % of its operating time. Additionally, with improved steam pressure control system, shut down for more than one third of its operating time was achievable. It resulted in the RES-based cogeneration unit electric energy output increase by approximately 1.2 GWh annually with estimated investment of ca. 20 ths. EUR. Additional cost saving measures were also proposed. The overall energy costs reduction achieved by proposed set of measures was 360 ths. EUR annually with estimated investment of 400 ths. EUR.

Introduction

In the past few decades, energy demand of industrial processes has been continuously rising. To decrease energy costs, two approaches are adopted in chemical industry: improving energy efficiency of manufacturing processes (i.e. decrease of energy consumption) and reducing amount of imported energy (i.e. decrease of energy unit cost)¹. Another issue to be addressed with the rise of energy demand is subsequent worsening environmental impact². Pulp and paper industry was listed as fourth largest energy consumer accounting for about 6 % of energy consumption in OECD industrial sector in 2012³. Therefore, improvement of energy efficiency in pulping and papermaking processes was frequently main subject of cost optimization activities in recent years^{4,5} and has a potential to significantly reduce global energy consumption of chemical industry.

Most of the energy consumed during papermaking processes is in the form of heat and electricity. Heat is provided by superheated steam and hot water where the energy source is largely based on biomass. To reduce amount of imported energy, electricity is usually generated on-site in central heat and power plant of a paper mill. In a conventional paper mill, majority of required steam amount is generated in a recovery boiler, where concentrated mixture of lignin and chemicals known as black liquor is burned and regenerated. To the most energy-intensive processes in an integrated mill producing pulp and paper usually belong chemical pulping, paper stock preparation, paper dewatering and recovery of chemicals^{6,7}.

In a unit called paper machine, pulp fibres in the form of paper stock are chemically and mechanically treated and converted into paper product in the paper dewatering section. Conventional paper dewatering section consists of three stages – web forming, press and drying section. First two stages work utilize mechanical principle (effect of gravitation, vacuum and mechanical compression) to remove water. Remaining moisture is removed in the drying section by evaporation. In Europe, drying section consists usually of drying cylinders that can be grouped into two parts, predrying and afterdrying section, divided by addition of starch solution as a filler^{8,9}. Although up to 99 % of water is removed in the mechanical dewatering step, the most expensive dewatering step is paper drying¹⁰. Water removal per kg of paper and relative cost of dewatering for every dewatering stage of the machine are summarized in Table I^{9,10}.

This contribution deals with cost optimization of paper machines operation and the impact of energy management measures on RES-based (based on Renewable Energy Sources) cogeneration unit performance. Paper machines under review belonged to one of the largest pulp and paper mills in Central Europe. Proposed

energy auditing procedure was based on previous activities¹¹. Cost saving measures presented in this paper are focused on heat utilization within the drying sections of reviewed paper machines. Semi-empirical mathematical model of paper machine is constructed to analyse complex process behaviour and to optimize energy demand of individual parts of drying section. Because of the conference contribution limitations, this paper provides close look only on one of the proposed cost saving measures and other measures are mentioned only briefly and quantified in the summary of achieved results. Proposed measures reduced consumptions of heat and electricity with emphasis on maintaining high quality of the final paper product.

Table I

Efficiency and cost distribution in dewatering process of conventional paper machine

Stage	Water removal per kg of paper [kg]	Relative cost of dewatering stage (%)
Web forming	up to 200	8-12
Press	2.4-2.8	10-15
Drying	1.0-1.4	75-80

Case study – introduction

Pulp and paper mill under study consisted of several paper machines producing different assortments of paper. Electricity was either directly purchased or generated on-site in mills own cogeneration units (composed of steam boilers and steam turbines) by combusting different fuels: black liquor, biomass and/or natural gas. Black liquor is concentrated mixture of lignin and chemical additives used in wood chips boiling and other pulp preparation processes. In the analysed time period of years 2013, 2014 and 2015, it was completely generated within the paper mill. Biomass was partially generated in the mill as a waste from raw wood processing and partially purchased on the market. Natural gas was purchased on the market only. It is necessary to state out that natural gas was used not only as a fuel in boilers but also as a reactive compound in the chemicals recovery process in the lime kiln. Figure 1 depicts increasing trend of purchased biomass consumption and indicates increased orientation of mills central heat and power plant towards RES-based cogeneration.

Figure 1. Annual amount of purchased biomass in the time period of 2013-2015

Subject of the presented cost saving measure was a paper machine producing approximately 55 000 t of paper with specific heat consumption of ca. 5.3 GJ/t of paper. In the analysed time period, mixture of hardwood and softwood pulp was used as a feedstock. After feedstock preparation, mechanical dewatering took place in web forming and press stage. Finally, partially dewatered pulp entered drying section consisting of 36 drying cylinders where predrying section includes 28 cylinders and afterdrying section includes remaining 8 cylinders. Paper machine model is drawn schematically in Figure 2. It consisted of mass and energy balances and was optimized to be in good agreement with operational data in the analysed time period. Paper machine was producing 18 different paper assortments differing mainly in paper basis weight (Figure 3) from 90 to 400 g/m² (because of

the data confidentiality, we refer to the paper assortments as A, B, etc.). Every paper assortment had a different optimal drying profile requiring different pressure levels of heating steam. Heat for the analyzed paper machine was provided by superheated steam with two pressure levels. Temperature and pressure of low-pressure level (LP) steam were in the range of 158-163 °C and 520 – 580 kPa, respectively. Temperature and pressure of middle-pressure level (MP) steam were in the range of 185-200 °C and 1110 – 1270 kPa, respectively. For preparation of steam with required pressure level for drying cylinders from LP and MP steam, thermocompressor was installed. For the purposes of energy management measures proposal, paper assortment A was selected as a reference case study because of its highest share in the production portfolio. For this paper assortment, measurements of key operating parameters of heat recovery system were performed.

Figure 2. Scheme of the analysed paper machine

Figure 3. Production share of different paper assortments produced by the analysed paper machine

Case study – results and discussion

As modelled and verified, ca. 120 kg of water per kg of paper was removed in the web forming and press stages, and ca. 1.1 kg of water per kg of paper was removed in the drying stage. Mathematical model coupled with measurement of operating parameters revealed low moisture of drying air leaving drying cylinders. It was achievable to increase the moisture by decreasing drying air flow. Such measure could increase the share of water removed in the drying section. However, due to problems with drying cylinders construction, decrease of drying air flow was not possible. The analysis of steam consumption and pressure levels provided insight into the operation of thermocompressor. The design ratio of LP to MP steam for the installed thermocompressor was 8.

The operating ratio was much lower with the maximum of ca. 4 and average value of ca. 1.2. This fact led to its ineffective operation and increased heat consumption of the paper machine in the form of more valuable MP steam. For approximately 13 % of thermocompressor operating time, its output pressure was lower than the input pressure of LP steam, i.e. thermocompressor served as a pressure reducing valve. In this time period, thermocompressor could be shut down and MP steam could be replaced by LP steam. Replacement of MP steam for LP steam effectively meant increase of the electricity produced in the cogeneration unit. The consequent lower overall electricity import also led to a reduction of global CO₂ and SO_x emissions associated with the electricity generation in a supplier power station.

Furthermore, recorded maximum and minimum pressure levels for drying cylinders as a function of produced paper assortments (Figure 4) were analyzed to determine necessary operating time of the installed thermocompressor. As it is depicted in Figure 4, for almost every paper assortment, pressure of LP steam was higher than maximum recorded pressure level, thus LP steam was satisfactory as heat source for predrying section of the drying stage. More detailed analysis revealed that only three drying cylinders in the afterdrying section required steam with higher pressure than LP steam pressure. If the heat source for these three drying cylinders was MP steam, required steam pressure could be achieved without operation of thermocompressor for approximately 40 % of its operating time. However, this measure required design of new pressure control system. For the drying cylinders with maximum required pressure lower than pressure of LP steam, direct input of LP steam from main distribution line was proposed. If the pressure of LP steam in the main distribution line would be too low, current pipeline route from thermocompressor should open. As it was previously stated, for remaining drying cylinders (three cylinders in the afterdrying section), direct input of MP steam from the main distribution line was proposed. Investment estimate for new pressure control system including costs of new software and new pipeline from the main distribution line directly to the drying cylinders was ca. 20 000 EUR. By this energy management measure, negligible heat reduction was achieved. However, more than 24 000 t of MP steam per year could be possibly replaced by LP steam resulting in the RES-based cogeneration unit electric energy output increase by approximately 1.2 GWh annually. Considering market prices of electricity and green energy subsidies, predicted reduction of energy costs was by ca. 80 000 EUR annually. Calculated internal rate of return was almost 400 %. Additional 16 000 t of MP steam per year could be replaced by LP steam if a new smaller thermocompressor would be installed. With the investment of ca. 100 000 EUR for new thermocompressor and costs reduction of ca. 50 000 EUR per year, calculated internal rate of return was less than 50 %. As a consequence of the unfavorable internal rate of return, this extra cost saving measure was not implemented.

Figure 4. Minimum and maximum levels of steam pressure in predrying and afterdrying section for different paper assortments produced by the analysed paper machine (dashed line – maximum recorded LP steam pressure of 580 kPa)

Other energy management measures formulated in the energy rationalization activity included shutdown of a thermocompressor in other paper machine, more efficient heat utilization contained in steam condensates, optimization of paper machine building heating system and replacement of an old small heat exchanger for a

modern bigger one. In this paragraph, principles of these energy management measures are discussed. Complete shutdown of a thermocompressor in other paper machine was possible because of the character of produced paper assortments not requiring steam with higher pressure. The installed thermocompressor was used to utilize low-pressure exhaust steam from condensate expansion tank with the help of MP steam. The exhaust steam mass flow was only ca. 50 kg/h and the MP steam required mass flow for this operation was up to 800 kg/h. However, the source of MP steam was located 1 km away from the thermocompressor that led to a heat loss by condensation in the inlet steam pipeline. Mathematical model of this paper machine (similar to the one depicted in Figure 2) revealed that the level of condensation was in the range of 200-500 kg/h of MP steam. With complete shutdown of thermocompressor, MP steam would be replaced by LP steam and the heat loss by condensation of MP steam would be avoided. With the investment of ca. 25 000 EUR for new pipeline segment and costs reduction of more than 40 000 EUR per year, calculated internal rate of return was ca. 170 %. The third energy management measure focused on installation of new heat exchanger to utilize the heat in steam condensate leaving paper machine with temperature of ca. 90 °C. This condensate could serve to increase temperature of dilution water that was otherwise heated by LP steam. Colder condensate would be heated and deaerated in the central heat and power plant by internal sources of waste heat. With the investment of ca. 160 000 EUR for new heat exchanger and its accessories, and costs reduction of more than 80 000 EUR per year, calculated internal rate of return was ca. 50 %. Optimization of paper machine building heating system required construction of a new heating system to increase heat exchange from supplied hot water to glycol solution used for building heating system. With the investment of ca. 150 000 EUR for the new heating system and costs reduction of ca. 100 000 EUR per year, calculated internal rate of return was less than 75 %. Principle of the last energy management measure was to increase heat flow from hot waste water in the process. To achieve this, new heat exchanger with larger heat exchanging area was proposed. With the investment of ca. 40 000 EUR for new modern bigger heat exchanger and its accessories, and costs reduction of more than 60 000 EUR per year, calculated internal rate of return was ca. 160 %. The whole set of energy management measures is summarized in Table II.

Table II
Set of the proposed energy management measures

Energy management measure	Investment [EUR]	Annual energy costs reduction (EUR)
Thermocompressor operation optimization and new pressure control system	20 000	80 000
Complete shutdown of thermocompressor in other paper machine	25 000	40 000
More efficient heat utilization contained in steam condensates	160 000	80 000
Building heating system optimisation	150 000	100 000
Replacement of an old small heat exchanger for a modern bigger one	40 000	60 000
Sum	395 000	360 000

Conclusion

This paper provided an insight into energy management of modern paper machines and impacts of its alterations on the overall economic profit of a pulp and paper mill. Paper machines belonging to one of the biggest pulp and paper mills in Central Europe were under review. Set of five energy management measures focused on the optimization of heat utilization in the papermaking process was proposed. Synergic effect of proposed energy management measures presented potential reduction of annual energy costs by approximately 360 000 EUR with required investment estimated to be of ca. 395 000 EUR. In this contribution, the most promising measure, optimization of thermocompressor operation coupled with new steam pressure control system for drying cylinders, was discussed in detail. Retrospective analysis of required steam pressure levels supported by the mathematical modelling results revealed possibility to shut down the thermocompressor for more than one third of its operating time. The measure effect was not direct heat saving, but opportunity to replace MP steam by LP steam leading to increase of the electricity produced in the RES-based cogeneration unit by approximately 1.2 GWh annually. The consequent lower overall electricity import also led to a reduction of global CO₂ and SO_x emissions produced during electricity generation in a supplier power station. Other complementary energy management measures were also briefly discussed with emphasis on the cost saving principle.

Proposed process optimization procedure employed critical retrospective study of historical operating data records and simplified mathematical models composed of mass and energy balances. Every energy management measure was analysed not only from the point of the reviewed production process, but its impact on the paper mills central heat and power plant operation was also taken into account. It was shown how this approach could lead to significant decrease of energy costs and therefore, contribute to sustainable development of modern chemical industry.

Literature

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